

Age of Foraging

0

1

Social Classification

- 0
- 1
- 2

Retreat Size with Eggs

Approximate Retreat Size Relative to Body Size

- 0 (Red)
- 1 (Light Pink)
- 2 (Light Grey)
- 3 (Blue)

Retreat Modification

- 0
- 1
- 2

Egg Sac Structure

How Egg Sac Attached or Carried

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3

- Thelcticopis* sp
- Heteropoda jugulans*
- Heteropoda tetrica*
- Heteropoda boiei*
- Heteropoda venatoria*
- Heteropoda davidbowie*
- Heteropoda lunula*
- Pandercetes cf malleator*
- Pandercetes cf nigrogularis*
- Barylestis variatus*
- Barylestis scutatus*
- Palystes superciliosus*
- Damastes* sp
- Olios giganteus*
- Olios* sp Tiny Singapore
- Eusparassus* sp
- Delena spenceri*
- Delena melanocheilus*
- Delena gloriosa*
- Delena lapidicola*
- Delena cancerides*
- Neosparassus calligaster*
- Isopeda villosa*
- Isopeda montana*
- Isopedella conspersa*
- Isopedella pessleri*
- Isopedella victorialis*
- Isopedella leai*
- Holconia nigrigularis*
- Isopeda leishmanni*
- Isopedella frenchi*
- Holconia flindersi*
- Holconia insignis*
- Holconia hirsuta*
- Typostola barbata*
- Typostola* sp tiger
- Pediana regina*
- Pediana horni*
- Beregama cordata*
- Beregama aurea*

Approximate Mass

Approximate Cephalothorax Width

- Thelcticopsis* sp
- Heteropoda jugulans*
- Heteropoda tetrica*
- Heteropoda boiei*
- Heteropoda venatoria*
- Heteropoda davidbowie*
- Heteropoda lunula*
- Pandercetes cf malleator*
- Pandercetes cf nigrogularis*
- Barylestis variatus*
- Barylestis scutatus*
- Palystes superciliosus*
- Damastes* sp
- Olios giganteus*
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